

Spiro-compounds. Part II. Ring Transformation in Spiro-compound from 4-Methylcyclohexanone. A New Synthesis of Cadalene.

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As it has not been possible to isolate the isomers demanded by Sachse's hypothesis (*Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1323) of two strainless forms of cyclohexane nor their monosubstituted or disubstituted derivatives (Werner and Conrad, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3046; Wightman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2541; Goldschmidt and Grafinger, *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 279; Day and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1063; Desai, Hunter, Khan and Sahariya, *ibid.*, 1936, 416) the postulate of Mohr (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, **98**, 318) that they are easily inter-convertible holds good. Thinking that the spiro-compounds from methylcyclohexanone may differ from their cyclohexanone analogues, their study has been taken up. Such difference in behaviour has actually been observed by Birch and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1821) and Desai (*ibid.*, 1932, 1049).

Freshly distilled 4-methylcyclohexanone cyanohydrin is allowed to react with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate and the sodium salt of ethyl 1-cyano-4-methylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate (I), thus obtained, is allowed to react with ethyl β -chloropropionate to yield diethyl 1-cyano-4-methylcyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate. On hydrolysis, the above ester yields an acid anhydride (II) (corresponding ester is obtained on esterification) from which the required 1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1- α -glutaric acid is obtained after treatment with alkali. Triethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate (III), obtained by esterifying the above acid, when subjected to the action of sodium in benzene yields diethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-spirocyclopentane-2'-one-3' : 5'-dicarboxylate (IV). It is hydrolysed by means of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) to yield 4-methylcyclohexane-spirocyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylic acid. The ester (V) of the above keto-acid is subjected to the action of methyl magnesium iodide when compound (VI) is obtained. It is observed that during dehydrogenation of the spiro-compound (VI) cadalene (VII) is obtained.

A large number of sesquiterpenes are stated to have naphthalene ring structure, the experimental basis for this being the fact that on sulphur or selenium dehydrogenation they give rise to cadalene or eudalene. But this conclusion is essentially based on the fact that whatever be the nature of ring structure that is initially present in them, it is not altered during this reaction. In view of certain observations described above, this conclusion is, however, not justifiable, though not impossible.

The spiro-compound (IV) obtained is found to differ in no way from *cyclohexane* analogue with respect to its formation (Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 536). As no suitable reagent could be found which preferentially attacks the one, leaving the other intact, nothing definite can be said at present as regards the difference in their stability, or in other words they may be said to have got equal stability.

From the consideration of the multiplaner structure of *cyclohexane* ring two or more isomers of the acids obtained are possible and work is in progress to separate them.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl 1-Cyano-4-methylcyclohexane-1-cyanoglutarate.—To a well cooled solution of freshly distilled 4-methylcyclohexane cyanohydrin (190 g.) in absolute alcohol (190 c.c.), a suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, obtained from ethyl cyanoacetate (168 g.), sodium (33 g.) and alcohol (500 c.c.), was gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture after being kept in ice for 6 hours and at room temperature for 3 days, was mixed with ethyl β -chloropropionate (125 g.) and after initial reaction had abated, boiled under reflux until a test portion, diluted with water was neutral to litmus (about 40 hours). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was washed with a large volume of water to remove most of the alcohol, dried and ether recovered. It distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. 208° - $215^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 150 g. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires C, 64.6; H, 7.7 per cent).

1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1- α -glutaric Acid.—The ester (20 g.) was mixed with 6 vols. of 70 % sulphuric acid and boiled under reflux for 12 hours. The condenser was removed from the flask from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether and the acid thus obtained, was freed from neutral matter by extraction with sodium carbonate. The resulting product (an acid anhydride) was heated on a water-bath with a solution of caustic alkali (15 %) for 3 to 4 hours. It was then acidified and extracted with ether. After removing ether, the product was kept in a desiccator when it solidified. It crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m.p. 155° , yield

10 g. (Found: C, 57·4; H, 7·4. $C_{13}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 57·3; H, 7·3 per cent).

The crude acid anhydride was esterified by passing alcohol vapour through a mixture of it in alcohol containing sulphuric acid. The product obtained after working up in the usual manner was found to distill in vacuum, but solidified on attaining the room temperature. It was crystallised from ether, m.p. 79°. (Found: C, 63·7; H, 8·1. $C_{15}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 63·8; H, 7·8 per cent).

Triethyl 4-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate was obtained from the acid by the alcohol vapour method. The acid (59 g.), absolute alcohol (159 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (14 c.c.), 6 litres of alcohol vaporised (7 hours) gave 60 g. of the ester, b.p. 175°-180/5 mm. (Found: C, 64·1; H, 8·9. $C_{19}H_{32}O_6$ requires C, 64·04; H, 8·9 per cent).

Diethyl 4-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-3':5'-dicarboxylate.—A mixture of the foregoing ester (20 g.) and granulated sodium (2·3 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil (8 g.), b.p. 180°-185°/4 mm. (Found: C, 65·7; H, 8·1. $C_{17}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 65·8; H, 8·3 per cent).

4-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylic Acid.—The ester was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20 %) for 12 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether, the extract washed with water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether it was kept in a desiccator when it crystallised as needles, m.p. 130° (after previous softening). (Found: C, 68·3; H, 8·5. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68·5; H, 8·5 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 15·3. $C_{13}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15·7 per cent).

Ethyl 4-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylate.—The ester prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (10 g.) in absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) with the addition of absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, formed a colourless viscous oil (10 g.), b.p. 133°/4 mm. (Found: C, 70·5; H, 9·2. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 70·5; H, 9·2 per cent).

Action of methyl magnesium iodide on Ethyl 4-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one 5'-carboxylate.—The ester (10 g.) diluted with dry ether (10 c.c.) was slowly added to a solution of methyl magnesium iodide (prepared from 3.6 g. of magnesium, 100 c.c. dry ether and 11 c.c. of methyl iodide) cooled in ice-water. After standing for 12 hours at the ordinary temperature, the product was decomposed with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was extracted several times with ether and the extract was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The brown residue was boiled with a solution of potassium hydroxide (10 g.) in water (10 c.c.) and alcohol (90 c.c.) for 1 hour; the alcohol removed and the residue diluted with water and repeatedly extracted with ether. (The alkaline solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and again extracted with ether when an acid is obtained.) On removing ether a neutral oil was obtained. This oil (5 g.) and selenium (30 g.) were heated at 290°-300° for 20 hours. The temperature was then raised to 330° and kept there for 30 hours. The product of reaction was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed several times with water and dilute alkali. On removing ether an oil was left which was converted into picrate. It was identified as cadalene picrate, m.p. 115° alone or mixed with an authentic sample of cadalene picrate.

Oxidation of 4-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylic Acid—The keto acid was warmed with an excess of concentrated nitric acid until most of the red fumes had been evolved. The resulting solution was then boiled for a few minutes, and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and again evaporated. The semi-solid mass thus obtained was heated when carbon dioxide escaped with the formation of hexahydro-*p*-toluic acid. It crystallised from formic acid, m.p., 111° (*lit.* 111°.)

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